

Dipole Moment Studies of Molecular Structure of Some Carboxylic Esters

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Electric dipole moments of several esters have been calculated at 25° using extrapolation method. The excess of moment over the theoretical value has been interpreted in terms of molecular configuration.

The general preference for the trans-plane configuration in the case of simple carboxylic esters suggests that there is an electrostatic attraction between the carbonyl oxygen and the group R_1 (fig. 1). But the calculated electric dipole moment for a rigid trans-plane configuration is, in the most cases of simple mono-carboxylic esters, lower than that of the

FIG 1 General ester molecule, (trans)

experimentally observed values. To account for such excess moment a typical configuration was established^{1,2}, in which the C-O-C plane lies considerably out of the trans-plane. The electron diffraction studies³ of several simple carboxylic esters also showed the possibility of intramolecular rotation or rotatory oscillation about the position of minimum potential energy. The existence of this kind of rotatory oscillation usually causes a slight increase in the electric dipole moment of the molecule. The present investigation has been carried out to study the molecular configuration of some of the mono-carboxylic esters by assuming the excess moment as due to the angular rotation of the C-O-C plane. The angle through which the C-O-C plane is rotated for all esters, has been calculated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Dielectric constants for the pure esters and their mixtures were determined at 2 mc/s using WTW heterodyne dipolemeter. The cell temperature was maintained at 25°. Benzene was used as the solvent. The extrapolation method was used to determine $P_{2\infty}$ and the values of dipole moments obtained agreed well with those by Helverstadt and Kumler's method⁴. Correction for the contribution of the distortion polarization was applied from R_D values. The uncertainty in the determination of the dipole moment is about 1 per cent.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Using standard molecular parameters⁵, confirmed by electron diffraction studies, the general value of electric dipole moment (μ_T), the value corresponding to the rigid trans-plane configuration, is calculated to be $1.6D$. The values of dipole moment (μ_θ) for all orientations of the C-O-C plane have been calculated and are recorded in Table 1. The angular rotation of the C-O-C plane is reasonably limited upto 60° as the existence of the C-O-C plane within this limitation is expected to be more probable.

TABLE 1

Dipole moment of the general ester molecule for various positions of the C-O-C plane

$$\mu_T = 1.6 D$$

θ	μ_θ in Debye unit	$\Delta\mu/\theta^2 \times 10^{-3}$
15	1.64	0.177
20	1.67	0.175
30	1.76	0.177
40	1.88	0.175
45	1.95	0.172
50	2.03	0.172
60	2.20	0.166

A comparative study of the observed and theoretically evaluated dipole moments indicates that the molecule of simple carboxylic esters possess a configuration in which the C-O-C plane lies more or less 30° out of the trans-plane. On such a reasonable assumption that the excess moment is entirely contributed by the angular rotation of the C-O-C plane, the molecules of simple carboxylic esters are supposed to have a typical configuration where the C-O-C plane is considered to be out of the trans-plane, making an angle θ with it. It leads to a conclusion that the excess moment and hence μ_θ should be a function of θ and may be expressed by the following general equation,

$$\mu_\theta = a + b\theta + c\theta^2 \quad \dots (1)$$

where θ may have all possible values between $-\pi/2$ and $\pi/2$.

From the principle of least squares, the normal equations reduce to

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma\mu_i &= a + b\Sigma\theta_i + c\Sigma\theta_i^2 \\ \Sigma\mu_i\theta_i &= a\Sigma\theta_i + b\Sigma\theta_i^2 + c\Sigma\theta_i^3 \\ \Sigma\mu_i\theta_i^2 &= a\Sigma\theta_i^2 + b\Sigma\theta_i^3 + c\Sigma\theta_i^4 \end{aligned} \quad \dots (2)$$

This method of evaluating the constants a , b and c is only approximate and the values are the one corresponding to the closest fit. Hence the equation must be simplified with the existing conditions. In the case of monocarboxylic esters the values of dipole moment (μ_θ) do not depend upon the nature of sign of θ . Since, in the case of mono-carboxylic esters, μ_θ remains unaltered for $\pm\theta$, b should necessarily be zero, also if $\theta \rightarrow 0$; $\mu_\theta \rightarrow \mu_T$. By applying these two conditions the equation (1) may be rewritten as

$$\mu_\theta = \mu_T + c\theta^2 \quad \dots (3)$$

In the case of simple carboxylic esters, where the excess moment is contributed by the angular rotation of the C-O-C plane, the value of c is found to be 0.173×10^{-3} .

FIG 2

If θ is the angle through which the C-O-C plane is rotated, its value can easily be determined with the knowledge of excess moment. The values of θ , the angle through which the C-O-C plane is rotated, for some mono-carboxylic esters have been calculated to account for the excess moment and are listed in Table 2.

TABLE 2

The angular rotation (θ) of the C-O-C plane in some simple esters

Ester	P_{∞}	μ in Debye	$\Delta\mu$ in Debye	θ
Methyl acetate	81.50	1.78	0.18	32° 4'
Ethyl acetate	92.90	1.82	0.22	35° 27'
Butyl acetate	100.00	1.83	0.23	36° 14'
Amyl acetate	106.00	1.85	0.25	37° 47'
Phenyl acetate	98.00	1.72	0.12	26° 10'

It is found that the values of θ given in Table 2 compare favourably with the values observed from the electron diffraction studies⁵. As θ increases, the carbonyl oxygen will have comparatively less influence upon the group R_1 . Hence the slight increase in θ in the

case of aliphatic esters with the bulkiness of the molecule R_1 may be due to the influence of the carbonyl oxygen on the R_1 group. In phenyl acetate the carbonyl oxygen may have a greater influence on R_1 because of the π -orbital electrons of the latter.

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